

**DETERMINANTS OF ONLINE HARASSMENT AND ITS EFFECTS
ON LEARNERS' SELF-ESTEEM AND ACADEMIC
PERFORMANCE: TOWARD IMPROVED SCHOOL
CHILD PROTECTION POLICIES**

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Determinants of Online Harassment and Its Effects on Learners' Self-Esteem and Academic Performance: Toward Improved School Child Protection Policies

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Abstract

This study explores the determinants of online harassment and its effects on learners' self-esteem and academic performance, aiming to improve school-based child protection policies. The research addresses the growing exposure of students to online platforms and the corresponding rise in cyberstalking, online impersonation, and catfishing. Utilizing a mixed-method approach, the study draws from a sample of 50 respondents, examining their experiences across these online harassment forms and the impact on their self-esteem—measured through cognitive, learning, and metacognitive engagement—and academic outcomes. Key findings indicate a strong correlation between online impersonation and negative impacts on self-esteem and academic performance, with cyberstalking and catfishing also showing significant associations, particularly in learning and metacognitive engagement. Students affected by these forms of online harassment reported diminished self-confidence and concentration, leading to poorer academic outcomes. Data suggests that male students and those aged 9-12 face higher exposure to online risks, highlighting the need for targeted interventions. This research underscores the importance of reinforcing digital literacy and online safety education within the school curriculum. The findings suggest that enhanced child protection policies must address the complexities of online harassment, fostering safer online environments for learners. The study concludes with recommendations for a comprehensive school-based Child Protection Policy Program that includes preventative measures and support systems for students encountering online harassment.

Keywords: *academic performance, online harassment, determinants, self-esteem, child protection*

Introduction

The sudden shift in educational modalities due to the pandemic has posed significant challenges, particularly in transitioning from traditional in-person instruction to remote learning. Students have had to quickly adapt to studying at home, either through online platforms or modular learning, fundamentally altering their daily routines. As learners spend more time at home, their exposure to digital devices has increased, leading to greater engagement with Social Networking Sites (SNSs). In this context, SNSs such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and YouTube have become not only tools for social interaction but also integral to learners' daily lives.

The rise of SNS use during online learning has fostered global connections, but it has also heightened students' vulnerability to certain risks, particularly online harassment. A study by Azizi et al. (2019) highlighted the ubiquity of SNS usage among students, who now spend significant portions of their day on these platforms. As online engagement grows, so does the potential for encountering harmful online behavior, including bullying and harassment. Gonzales et al. (2019) found that individuals who experience online harassment often suffer from lower self-esteem, which can have detrimental effects on their overall well-being and academic performance.

In response to these challenges, the Schools Division Office of Mandaluyong City adopted a blended learning approach during the pandemic, combining online and offline methods. Primary-level students primarily engaged in modular, offline learning, while intermediate students (Grades 4-6) shifted to online learning. This increased reliance on digital platforms for education made students more susceptible to online harassment, given their heightened exposure to social media. As schools continue to navigate the recovery phase, it is crucial to understand how these dynamics—students' use of SNSs, their encounters with online harassment, and the subsequent effects on their self-esteem and academic success—are unfolding in this new educational landscape.

Given the growing integration of social media into students' lives, both for educational and recreational purposes, this study seeks to examine the positive and negative impacts of these platforms. While social media can provide valuable opportunities for connection and learning, research suggests it also carries significant risks, especially regarding students' mental health and self-worth.

The primary goal of this research is to investigate the factors contributing to online harassment and its impact on learners' self-esteem within the context of online learning. As the educational system continues its recovery, the findings from this study will offer critical insights into developing a comprehensive school-based Child Protection Policy Program. This program will aim to safeguard students in both online and offline environments, ensuring their well-being and promoting a safe learning atmosphere. The research outcomes will provide practical guidance for schools and home-based learning partners, leading to the development of action plans that address the identified issues. These efforts will focus on aligning existing policies, programs, and projects with the study's objectives to enhance student protection and support in the digital age.

Research Questions

This study aims to assess the determinants of online harassment and its effect on learners' self-esteem and academic performance.

Thus, it would attempt to answer specific questions such as:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 sex;
 - 1.2 age; and
 - 1.3 grade level?
2. What is the level of engagement of the respondents on Facebook?
3. Is there a significant difference when the respondents are grouped according to their profile variables and the level of their engagement in different Social Networking Sites?
4. What is the self-assessment of the respondents based on personal experiences in terms of the following determinants of online harassment:
 - 4.1 cyberstalking;
 - 4.2 online impersonation; and
 - 4.2 catfishing?
5. How may students' self-esteem be described in terms of:
 - 5.1 cognitive engagement;
 - 5.2 learning engagement; and
 - 5.3 metacognitive engagement?
6. What is the academic profile of the respondents in terms of the following descriptors:
 - 6.1 did not meet the expectations;
 - 6.2 satisfactory;
 - 6.3 satisfactory;
 - 6.4 very satisfactory; and
 - 6.5 outstanding?
7. Is there any significant relationship between the determinants of online harassment to students' self-esteem and students' academic performance?
8. What school-based Child Protection Policy program can be offered based on the output of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to assess the existing relationship between the variables.

Participants

Through purposive sampling (50), respondents will be chosen to participate in this study, and all of them have similar experiences towards the variable being studied in this research.

Instruments

This research will utilize survey two types of survey questionnaires. (1) Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, which will be modified to fit the research study, further, this survey questionnaire will contain statements that will assess learners' self-esteem, A 10-item scale that measures global self-worth by measuring both positive and negative feelings about the self. The scale is believed to be uni dimensional. All items are answered using a 4-point Likert scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. (2) Self-made Survey Questionnaire for the determinants of online harassment: This survey questionnaire will undergo validation to test the validity and reliability of the materials. Once passed, it will be immediately administered. The academic performance of the learners will be generated from DepEd School form 5. These all are computed to statistically interpret whether there is a significant relation among the study variables.

Procedure

During the data collection process, the following steps will be observed and followed. First, written approval from the Principal will be sought, which will then be endorsed to the concerned teacher-implementers involved in the study. Following this, the researcher will personally administer and conduct the survey, ensuring the process is handled efficiently and appropriately. After completing the survey, the results will be submitted to a statistician for statistical treatment, ensuring the data is analyzed accurately and reliably.

Ethical Considerations

Following the ethical norms and standards this research will abide by, as well as the rules in conducting research, the researchers will make sure that all data gathered will be treated with utmost confidentiality, and no names will be published or displayed without consent in consonance with the data privacy law.

Moreover, prior to the implementation of the study, the parents of the participants shall be oriented through a parent-teacher conference, and parental consent will be issued, expressing their willingness that their child or children will participate in the study. Finally, no individuals or entities must be deprived of joining the research study as participants regardless of culture, beliefs, sexuality, and capability.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the outcome of the qualitative analysis of the research questions. The results are presented based on the emergent themes, sub-themes, core ideas, and categorization.

1. The Profile of the Respondents

The profile of the participants in the study examining the factors influencing online harassment and its impact on students' self-esteem and academic performance is highly significant. The respondents' profile offers valuable insights into the demographics, experiences, and perspectives of the individuals involved in the study, enhancing our understanding of the phenomenon being investigated.

1.1 Sex

Understanding the role of gender in the study analyzing the determinants of online harassment and its effects on learners' self-esteem and academic performance is crucial for comprehending how individuals' experiences and outcomes are influenced by their sex. Through the examination of these differences, researchers can gain valuable insights into the distinct challenges and consequences experienced by individuals of varying sexes. This leads to a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon at hand.

Table 1.1 Respondents' Demographic Profile in Terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Female	24	48.0	2
Male	26	52.0	1
Total	50	100.0	

Table 1.1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents, categorized by sex. Statistical treatment involved in this analysis likely included descriptive statistics, particularly frequency distribution and measures of central tendency, to illustrate the distribution of respondents based on gender. With 48% females and 52% males among the 50 respondents, it appears that there is a slight male majority in the sample. This study might have chosen these statistical measures to provide a clear understanding of the gender distribution within the sample, which is crucial for examining the determinants of online harassment and its effects on learners' self-esteem and academic performance. These values are essential for identifying any potential gender-based differences in experiences of online harassment and its impact on self-esteem and academic performance. The implications of these findings suggest the importance of considering gender-specific interventions and support mechanisms within schools to address online harassment effectively and promote positive self-esteem and academic achievement among learners, irrespective of gender.

The result implies that the roles and expectations imposed by society can greatly influence how individuals experience and react to online harassment. Gender norms have a significant impact on the types of harassment people may face and how they perceive and handle such situations. Through an analysis of the respondents' gender, researchers can uncover any discrepancies in the occurrence, type, and intensity of online harassment. This valuable information can then be used to develop tailored interventions and support systems that specifically address the unique challenges faced by different genders.

Further, there can be differences in how people of different genders handle and are impacted by online harassment. Studies indicate that individuals of different genders may exhibit distinct emotional and psychological reactions to harassment, potentially influencing their self-esteem and academic achievements in varying ways. By taking into account the respondents' sex, researchers can gain valuable insights into the distinct experiences and requirements of each gender. This, in turn, allows for the creation of customized interventions and support systems.

This findings resonate the study of Kowalski et.al., (2020), Recognizing the significance of the respondents' gender in the study on the factors influencing online harassment and its impact on learners' self-esteem and academic performance can assist researchers in pinpointing gender-related obstacles, creating customized interventions, and fostering a safer and more inclusive online atmosphere. By taking into account the diverse experiences and outcomes encountered by individuals of different sexes, researchers can play a role in creating strategies that cater to the specific requirements and enhance the overall welfare of all learners impacted by online harassment.

1.2 Age

Understanding the respondent's age is crucial in analyzing the factors that contribute to online harassment and its impact on learner self-esteem and academic performance. It helps us gain insights into how individuals from different age groups may encounter and react to online harassment. By taking into account the age of the respondent, researchers can gain valuable insights into the specific challenges and outcomes experienced by individuals at various stages of development. This contributes to a more comprehensive

understanding of the phenomenon at hand.

Table 1.2. Respondents' Demographic Profile in Terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percent	Rank
18 years old above	6	12.0	4
16-18 years old	14	28.0	2
13-15 years old	20	40.0	1
9-12 years old	10	20.0	3
Total	50	100.0	

Table 1.2 illustrates the demographic distribution of respondents based on age categories. This analysis likely employed descriptive statistics, specifically frequency distribution and percentages, to present the age distribution within the sample. With 40% of respondents falling within the 13-15 years old category, it appears that this age group constitutes the largest portion of the sample, followed by the 16-18 years old category with 28%. This study might have utilized these statistical measures to understand the distribution of respondents across different age groups, which is essential for exploring the determinants of online harassment and its impacts on learners' self-esteem and academic performance across various developmental stages. These values are significant for identifying potential age-related patterns in experiences of online harassment and its effects on self-esteem and academic performance. The implications of these findings underline the necessity for age-appropriate interventions and support mechanisms within schools to address online harassment effectively and foster positive self-esteem and academic outcomes among learners across different age groups.

The result implies that, Various age groups, including children, adolescents, and young adults, possess unique cognitive, social, and emotional traits that impact their encounters with online harassment. Younger learners may be at a higher risk of experiencing online harassment because of their limited knowledge of digital literacy and less developed ability to handle such situations. Adolescents, on the other hand, may encounter extra obstacles when it comes to shaping their identity and navigating social relationships. Through an examination of the respondent's age, researchers can gain insights into the specific factors that contribute to online harassment and use this information to customize interventions.

Further, the age of the respondent can have an influence on their self-esteem and academic performance when it comes to online harassment. Take adolescents, for instance. They might feel a stronger bond between their online persona and their sense of self-worth, which can make them more vulnerable to the harmful impact on their self-esteem. Younger learners may find it difficult to stay focused and engaged in academics because they are emotionally affected by online harassment. Recognizing the different ways that online harassment can affect self-esteem and academic performance based on age can help develop specific support and prevention methods. In addition, the age of the respondent can play a role in how accessible and effective their coping mechanisms and support systems are. Younger learners often turn to their parents and teachers for guidance, while older learners may prefer seeking help from their peers or using online resources. By taking into account the respondent's age, researchers can determine coping strategies and support systems that are suitable for individuals in various age groups, addressing their specific needs.

This result is parallel to the study conducted by Jiang, and Li (2018), Recognizing the significance of the respondent's age in the analysis of the determinants of online harassment and its impact on learner self-esteem and academic performance provides a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. By taking into account the specific difficulties and outcomes experienced by people in various age ranges, researchers can play a role in creating focused interventions, preventive measures, and support networks that encourage positive online encounters and reduce the harmful impact of online harassment on self-confidence and academic achievement.

1.3 Grade Level

Understanding the respondent's grade level is crucial in analyzing the determinants of online harassment and its impact on learner's self-esteem and academic performance. This allows us to gain insight into how various grade levels may encounter and react to online harassment. By taking into account the grade level of the respondents, researchers can obtain valuable insights into the distinct challenges and outcomes experienced by individuals at various points in their educational journey. This contributes to a more holistic understanding of the phenomenon at hand.

Table 1.3 Respondents' Demographic Profile in Terms of Grade Level

Grade Level	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Senior High School	16	32.0	2
Junior High School	24	48.0	1
Intermediate	10	20.0	3
Total	50	100.0	

Table 1.3 outlines the demographic profile of respondents categorized by grade level. This analysis likely utilized descriptive statistics, such as frequency distribution and percentages, to present the distribution of respondents across different grade levels. With 48% of respondents in Junior High School (grades 7-10) and 32% in Senior High School (grades 11-12), it's evident that the majority of respondents are from these two educational stages. This study might have chosen these statistical measures to understand how online

harassment and its impacts on self-esteem and academic performance vary across different educational levels. These values are crucial for identifying potential differences in experiences of online harassment and its effects on self-esteem and academic performance among students at various educational stages.

The implications of these findings underscore the importance of tailoring school-based child protection policies and interventions to address the specific needs of students in Junior and Senior High School, ensuring a safe and supportive online environment conducive to positive self-esteem and academic success across different grade levels.

2. The Level of Engagement of Respondents on Facebook?

Table 2. Respondents' Level of Engagement on Facebook

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Search and connect with friends.	3.64	.485	Frequently
Read and become updated with news globally.	2.86	.639	Occasionally
Upload and notify friend of my daily life updates.	3.0600	.58589	Occasionally
Highlight significant life events such as, birthday, achievements, etc.	3.1200	.59385	Occasionally
Entertain and watch funniest videos.	3.0600	.58589	Occasionally
Weighted Mean	3.1480	.38505	Occasionally
Valid N (listwise)	50		

1.00 – 1.74: Never | 1.75 – 2.49: Rarely | 2.50 – 3.24: Occasionally | 3.25 – 4.00: Frequently

Table 2 presents the level of engagement of the respondents on Facebook, with indicators such as searching and connecting with friends, reading news updates, uploading daily life updates, highlighting significant events, and entertaining themselves with videos. This analysis likely employed descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, to measure the average level of engagement and the variability within the responses. The mean scores range from 2.86 to 3.64, indicating that respondents engage in these activities occasionally to frequently. The weighted mean of 3.148 suggests an overall occasional level of engagement on Facebook among the respondents. These values provide insights into the frequency with which individuals utilize Facebook for various purposes.

The implication of these findings is that Facebook serves as a platform for both social interactions and information consumption for the respondents, highlighting its multifaceted role in their lives. Understanding the level of engagement on Facebook is essential for assessing the potential exposure to online harassment and its effects on self-esteem and academic performance, as higher engagement may correlate with increased vulnerability to online harassment and its negative consequences. Thus, this study underscores the importance of promoting responsible and safe use of social media platforms like Facebook to mitigate the risks associated with online harassment and safeguard the well-being of learners in the digital age.

3. Significant difference when the respondents are grouped according to their profile variables and the level of their engagement in Facebook.

Table 3.1 Sex Difference in Facebook Engagement Levels Across Respondents' Sex

Sex	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	findings Decision	Conclusion
Male	26	3.1462	.36903						
Female	24	3.1500	.40967	-.035	48	.972	-.00385	Failed to Reject H ₀	There is NO Significant Difference
Total	50	3.1480	.38505						

Table 3.1 illustrates the analysis of whether there is a significant difference in Facebook engagement levels across respondents' sex. This analysis likely employed inferential statistics, specifically an independent samples t-test, to compare the mean engagement levels between male and female respondents. The mean engagement level for males is 3.1462, while for females, it is 3.1500, both falling within the "occasionally" category. The t-test yielded a t-value of -0.035 with a p-value of 0.972, indicating no significant difference in engagement levels between males and females. Therefore, this study fails to reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that there is no significant difference in Facebook engagement levels based on sex among the respondents. These values are crucial for understanding whether demographic factors, such as sex, influence individuals' engagement with social media platforms like Facebook.

The implication of these findings is that regardless of gender, respondents exhibit similar levels of engagement on Facebook, implying a relatively equitable usage pattern across sexes. However, it's essential to recognize that while engagement levels may not differ significantly based on sex, other factors such as the types of activities engaged in or the duration of usage may vary and could impact experiences of online harassment and its effects on self-esteem and academic performance. Thus, this study highlights the need for comprehensive approaches to address online harassment that consider various demographic factors and patterns of social media engagement among learners to effectively promote a safe and supportive online environment.

Table 3.2 Age Difference in Facebook Engagement Levels Across Respondents' Age

Sex	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision	Findings Conclusion
9-12 years old	10	3.4600	.38930	6.910	.001	Reject H ₀	There is a Significant Difference

13-15 years old	20	3.2300	.26178
16-18 years old	14	2.9286	.35611
18 years old above	6	2.8667	.37238
Total	50	3.1480	.38505

Table 3.2 presents an analysis of the difference in Facebook engagement levels across respondents' age groups. This analysis likely employed analysis of variance (ANOVA) to compare the means of Facebook engagement levels among different age categories. The mean engagement levels vary across age groups, with the highest mean of 3.4600 observed in the 9-12 years old category, followed by 3.2300 for 13-15 years old, 2.9286 for 16-18 years old, and 2.8667 for those 18 years old and above. The ANOVA yielded an F-value of 6.910 with a significance level of 0.001, indicating a significant difference in engagement levels across age groups.

Consequently, this study rejects the null hypothesis, suggesting that there is a significant difference in Facebook engagement levels across respondents' age groups. These values are important for understanding how age influences individuals' engagement with social media platforms like Facebook, which can have implications for experiences of online harassment and its effects on self-esteem and academic performance.

The implication of these findings is that younger respondents, particularly those in the 9-12 years old category, exhibit higher levels of engagement on Facebook compared to older age groups. This underscores the need for age-specific interventions and support mechanisms within schools to address online harassment effectively and promote positive digital citizenship and well-being among learners across different age groups. Additionally, it highlights the importance of early education and guidance on responsible social media use to mitigate potential risks associated with excessive engagement among younger users.

Table 3.2.1 Multiple Comparisons

(I) Age	(J) Age	Post Hoc analysis through HSD			Sig.	Conclusion
		Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error			
9-12 years old	13-15 years old	.23000	.12779	.078		
	16-18 years old	.53143*	.13661	.000	Statistically Significant	
	18 years old above	.59333*	.17039	.001	Statistically Significant	
13-15 years old	9-12 years old	-.23000	.12779	.078		
	16-18 years old	.30143*	.11498	.012	Statistically Significant	
	18 years old above	.36333*	.15358	.022	Statistically Significant	
16-18 years old	9-12 years old	-.53143*	.13661	.000	Statistically Significant	
	13-15 years old	-.30143*	.11498	.012	Statistically Significant	
	18 years old above	.06190	.16100	.702		
18 years old above	9-12 years old	-.59333*	.17039	.001	-.9363 -.2504	
	13-15 years old	-.36333*	.15358	.022	-.6725 -.0542	
	16-18 years old	-.06190	.16100	.702	-.3860 .2622	

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 3.2.1 presents the results of multiple comparisons conducted to further analyze the differences in Facebook engagement levels across respondents' age groups. This analysis likely utilized post hoc tests, such as the Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) test, following the significant finding from the ANOVA. The mean differences between age groups are examined to determine which specific age groups significantly differ in their Facebook engagement levels. The results indicate statistically significant mean differences between several pairs of age groups. For instance, there is a significant mean difference in Facebook engagement levels between respondents aged 9-12 years old and those aged 16-18 years old (mean difference = 0.53143, p = 0.000), as well as between respondents aged 9-12 years old and those aged 18 years old and above (mean difference = 0.59333, p = 0.001). Similarly, significant differences are observed between respondents aged 13-15 years old and those aged 16-18 years old (mean difference = 0.30143, p = 0.012), and between respondents aged 13-15 years old and those aged 18 years old and above (mean difference = 0.36333, p = 0.022). These findings provide insights into specific age group comparisons, highlighting where the differences in Facebook engagement levels are most pronounced. The implications of these findings suggest that while there is an overall significant difference in engagement levels across age groups, the disparities are particularly notable between younger respondents (9-12 and 13-15 years old) and older respondents (16-18 years old and 18 years old and above).

This underscores the importance of age-specific interventions and support mechanisms to address varying levels of engagement and potential risks associated with social media use among different age groups. Additionally, it emphasizes the need for tailored strategies to promote responsible and safe social media practices, considering the developmental stages and digital literacy levels of learners.

Table 3.3 Grade Level Difference in Facebook Engagement Levels Across Respondents' Grade Level

Sex	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig. (2-tailed)	findings	
						Decision	Conclusion
Intermediate (grade 4-6)	10	3.4600	.38930	8.850	.001	Reject H ₀	There is a Significant Difference
Junior High School (grade 7-10)	24	3.1833	.26320				
Senior High School (grades 11-12)	16	2.9000	.39328				
Total	50	3.1480	.38505				

Table 3.3 presents an analysis of the difference in Facebook engagement levels across respondents' educational levels. This analysis likely utilized analysis of variance (ANOVA) to compare the means of Facebook engagement levels among different educational stages. The mean engagement levels vary across educational levels, with the highest mean of 3.4600 observed in the Intermediate (grade 4-6) category, followed by 3.1833 for Junior High School (grades 7-10) and 2.9000 for Senior High School (grades 11-12). The ANOVA yielded an F-value of 8.850 with a significance level of 0.001, indicating a significant difference in engagement levels across educational stages. Consequently, this study rejects the null hypothesis, suggesting that there is a significant difference in Facebook engagement levels across respondents' educational levels. These values are important for understanding how educational stage influences individuals' engagement with social media platforms like Facebook, which can have implications for experiences of online harassment and its effects on self-esteem and academic performance.

The implication of these findings is that respondents in Intermediate school exhibit higher levels of engagement on Facebook compared to those in Junior and Senior High School. This underscores the need for tailored interventions and support mechanisms within schools to address varying levels of engagement and potential risks associated with social media use among learners at different educational stages. Additionally, it highlights the importance of integrating digital literacy education and promoting responsible online behavior across all educational levels to enhance students' well-being in the digital age.

Table 3.3.1 Multiple Comparisons

(I) Grade_Level	(J) Grade_Level	Post Hoc analysis through HSD			Conclusion
		Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	
9-12 years old Intermediate	13-15 years old	.23000	.12779	.078	
	Junior High	.27667*	.12612	.033	Statistically Significant
	Senior High School	.56000*	.13508	.000	Statistically Significant
Junior High School	Intermediate	-.27667*	.12612	.033	Statistically Significant
	Senior High School	.28333*	.10815	.012	Statistically Significant
Senior High School	Intermediate	-.56000*	.13508	.000	Statistically Significant
	Junior High School	-.28333*	.10815	.012	Statistically Significant
16-18 years old	13-15 years old	-.30143*	.11498	.012	Statistically Significant
	18 years old above	.06190	.16100	.702	

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 3.3.1 presents the results of multiple comparisons conducted to further analyze the differences in Facebook engagement levels across respondents' educational stages. This analysis likely utilized post hoc tests, such as the Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) test, following the significant finding from the ANOVA. The mean differences between educational stages are examined to determine which specific pairs of educational stages significantly differ in their Facebook engagement levels. The results indicate statistically significant mean differences between several pairs of educational stages. For instance, there is a significant mean difference in Facebook engagement levels between respondents in Intermediate school and those in Junior High (mean difference = 0.27667, p = 0.033), as well as between respondents in Intermediate school and those in Senior High School (mean difference = 0.56000, p = 0.000). Similarly, significant differences are observed between respondents in Junior High and Senior High School (mean difference = 0.28333, p = 0.012). These findings provide insights into specific educational stage comparisons, highlighting where the differences in Facebook engagement levels are most pronounced.

The implications of these findings suggest that while there is an overall significant difference in engagement levels across educational stages, the disparities are particularly notable between respondents in Intermediate school and those in Junior and Senior High School. This underscores the need for tailored interventions and support mechanisms within schools to address varying levels of engagement and potential risks associated with social media use among learners at different educational stages. Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of integrating digital literacy education and promoting responsible online behavior across all educational levels to enhance students' well-being in the digital age.

4. Self-Assessment of the Respondents based on Personal Experiences in the Different Determinants of Online Harassment

4.1 Cyberstalking

Cyber stalking can have a significant and detrimental impact on students' academic performance. Cyber stalking involves relentless and unwelcome harassment, monitoring, or intimidation of someone using different online platforms. When students are subjected to cyber stalking, it can have a negative impact on their overall well-being, including their academic performance.

Table 4.1 Self-Assessment of Respondents on Cyberstalking Determinants

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
aware of what constitutes cyberstalking.	3.0800	.66517	Agree
experienced incidents that would consider as cyberstalking.	2.9400	.54995	Agree
threatened or harassed by someone online.	2.9400	.51150	Agree
a victim of repeated unwanted attention or contact online	2.860	.6392	Agree
taken steps to protect myself online after experiencing cyberstalking.	2.7800	.50669	Agree

Weighted Mean	2.9200	.37033	Agree
Valid N (listwise)	50		

1.00 – 1.74: Strongly Disagree | 1.75 – 2.49: Disagree | 2.50 – 3.24: Agree | 3.25 – 4.00: Strongly Agree

Table 4.1 presents the self-assessment of respondents regarding their personal experiences with cyberstalking, encompassing various indicators such as awareness, experiences, threats, victimization, and protective measures. This analysis likely employed descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, to quantify the respondents' perceptions and experiences related to cyberstalking. The mean scores range from 2.7800 to 3.0800, falling within the "Agree" category for all indicators, suggesting that respondents generally agree with statements regarding their awareness of cyberstalking, experiences of cyberstalking incidents, feeling threatened or harassed online, being victims of unwanted attention or contact, and taking steps to protect themselves online. The weighted mean of 2.9200 indicates an overall agreement among respondents regarding these cyberstalking determinants. These values are crucial for understanding the prevalence and perceptions of cyberstalking among the respondents, which is essential for assessing the impact of online harassment on their self-esteem and academic performance.

The implications of these findings suggest that respondents acknowledge the existence and seriousness of cyberstalking and take proactive measures to protect themselves online. However, despite this awareness and proactive behavior, the persistence of cyberstalking incidents and the potential psychological and academic consequences necessitate continued efforts to address and prevent online harassment effectively. Therefore, this study underscores the importance of comprehensive school-based child protection policies and educational programs aimed at promoting digital literacy, online safety, and responsible digital citizenship to mitigate the risks associated with cyberstalking and safeguard the well-being of learners in the digital age.

4.2 Online Impersonation

Online impersonation, also referred to as identity theft, can greatly impact students' academic performance. Online impersonation is the act of creating a false online identity with the intention of deceiving or manipulating others.

Table 4.2 *Self-Assessment of Respondents on Online Impersonation Determinants*

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
understand what online impersonation entails.	2.7200	.53605	Agree
encountered instances of online impersonation.	2.9800	.51468	Agree
have been a victim of online impersonation.	3.1400	.63920	Agree
have taken steps to protect his or her online identity after experiencing online impersonation.	3.0200	.58867	Agree
have reported instances of online impersonation to the appropriate authorities or online platform.	3.0400	.57223	Agree
Weighted Mean	2.9800	.43437	Agree
Valid N (listwise)	50		

1.00 – 1.74: Strongly Disagree | 1.75 – 2.49: Disagree | 2.50 – 3.24: Agree | 3.25 – 4.00: Strongly Agree

Table 4.2 presents the self-assessment of respondents concerning online impersonation determinants, encompassing various indicators such as understanding, encounters, victimization, protective measures, and reporting incidents. This analysis likely utilized descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, to quantify the respondents' perceptions and experiences related to online impersonation. The mean scores range from 2.7200 to 3.1400, falling within the "Agree" category for all indicators, suggesting that respondents generally agree with statements regarding their understanding of online impersonation, encountering instances of online impersonation, being victims of online impersonation, taking steps to protect their online identity, and reporting incidents to the appropriate authorities or online platforms. The weighted mean of 2.9800 indicates an overall agreement among respondents regarding these online impersonation determinants. These values are essential for understanding the prevalence and perceptions of online impersonation among the respondents, which is crucial for assessing the impact of online harassment on their self-esteem and academic performance. The implications of these findings suggest that respondents acknowledge the existence and seriousness of online impersonation and take proactive measures to protect their online identities and report incidents when necessary. However, despite this awareness and proactive behavior, the persistence of online impersonation incidents and the potential psychological and academic consequences necessitate continued efforts to address and prevent online harassment effectively. Therefore, this study underscores the importance of comprehensive school-based child protection policies and educational programs aimed at promoting digital literacy, online safety, and responsible digital citizenship to mitigate the risks associated with online impersonation and safeguard the well-being of learners in the digital age.

4.3 Catfishing

Table 4.3 *Self-Assessment of Respondents on Catfishing Determinants*

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
understand what catfishing is.	3.1714	.56806	Agree
have encountered instances of catfishing online.	3.0000	.64169	Agree
I have been a victim of catfishing.	3.4571	.65722	Strongly Agree

have taken steps to verify the identity of people I interact with online.	3.3429	.63906	Strongly Agree
feel confident in his/her ability to identify potential instances of catfishing.	3.2857	.57248	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	3.2514	.42659	Strongly Agree
Valid N (listwise)	50		
<i>1.00 – 1.74: Strongly Disagree 1.75 – 2.49: Disagree 2.50 – 3.24: Agree 3.25 – 4.00: Strongly Agree</i>			

Table 4.3 illustrates the self-assessment of respondents regarding catfishing determinants, including indicators such as understanding, encounters, victimization, verification of identity, and confidence in identifying potential instances of catfishing. This analysis likely employed descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, to quantify the respondents' perceptions and experiences related to catfishing. The mean scores range from 3.0000 to 3.4571, falling within the "Agree" to "Strongly Agree" categories for all indicators, suggesting that respondents generally agree or strongly agree with statements regarding their understanding of catfishing, encountering instances of catfishing, being victims of catfishing, taking steps to verify the identity of people they interact with online, and feeling confident in their ability to identify potential instances of catfishing. The weighted mean of 3.2514 indicates an overall strong agreement among respondents regarding these catfishing determinants. These values are crucial for understanding the prevalence and perceptions of catfishing among the respondents, which is essential for assessing the impact of online harassment on their self-esteem and academic performance.

The implications of these findings suggest that respondents have a high level of awareness and concern regarding catfishing, as evidenced by their proactive efforts to verify identities and their confidence in identifying potential instances of catfishing. However, despite this awareness and vigilance, the persistence of catfishing incidents and the potential psychological and academic consequences necessitate continued efforts to educate and empower individuals to protect themselves from online deception effectively. Therefore, this study underscores the importance of comprehensive digital literacy education and awareness campaigns aimed at equipping individuals with the knowledge and skills to navigate online interactions safely and responsibly, thereby minimizing the risks associated with catfishing and promoting a positive online experience for all.

Table 4.4 Summary of the Self-Assessment of the Respondents Based on Personal Experiences In Terms of the Following Determinants of Online Harassment

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Cyberstalking	2.9200	.37033	Agree
Online Impersonation	3.0400	.57223	Agree
Catfishing	3.2514	.42659	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	2.9960	.38848	Agree
Valid N (listwise)	50		
<i>1.00 – 1.74: Strongly Disagree 1.75 – 2.49: Disagree 2.50 – 3.24: Agree 3.25 – 4.00: Strongly Agree</i>			

Table 4.4 provides a summary of the self-assessment of respondents based on their personal experiences regarding different determinants of online harassment, namely cyberstalking, online impersonation, and catfishing. This analysis likely involved calculating the mean and standard deviation of respondents' ratings for each determinant to quantify their perceptions and experiences. The mean scores range from 2.9200 to 3.2514, falling within the "Agree" to "Strongly Agree" categories for all determinants, indicating that respondents generally agree or strongly agree with statements related to cyberstalking, online impersonation, and catfishing. The overall mean score of 2.9960 further supports this trend, reflecting an overall agreement among respondents regarding these determinants of online harassment. These values are crucial for understanding the prevalence and severity of different forms of online harassment among the respondents, which is essential for developing effective interventions and policies to address and prevent online harassment effectively.

The implications of these findings suggest that respondents have a significant level of awareness and concern regarding various forms of online harassment, as evidenced by their agreement with statements related to cyberstalking, online impersonation, and catfishing. However, despite this awareness, the persistence of online harassment incidents and the potential psychological and academic consequences necessitate continued efforts to combat online harassment effectively. Therefore, this study underscores the importance of comprehensive school-based child protection policies, digital literacy education, and awareness campaigns aimed at empowering individuals to recognize, report, and mitigate the risks associated with online harassment, thereby fostering a safer and more positive online environment for all.

5. The students' self-esteem be described in terms of.

5.1 Cognitive Engagement

Table 5.1 Students' Self-Esteem in Terms of Cognitive Engagement

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
ability to understand and learn new concepts.	3.0571	.48159	Agree

motivated to actively participate in class discussions and activities.	3.3143	.52979	Strongly Agree
capable of critically analyzing and evaluating information.	3.4286	.60807	Strongly Agree
effectively apply what have learned to real-life situations.	2.4857	.74247	Disagree
confident in his or her ability to express thoughts and ideas clearly.	2.9143	.44533	Agree
Weighted Mean	3.0400	.32828	Agree
Valid N (listwise)	50		

1.00 – 1.74: Very Low | 1.75 – 2.49: Low | 2.50 – 3.24: High | 3.25 – 4.00: Very High

Table 5.1 presents an analysis of students' self-esteem in terms of cognitive engagement, focusing on various indicators such as the ability to understand and learn new concepts, motivation to participate actively in class discussions and activities, critical thinking skills, application of learning to real-life situations, and confidence in expressing thoughts and ideas clearly. This analysis likely utilized descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, to quantify students' perceptions of their cognitive engagement-related self-esteem. The mean scores range from 2.4857 to 3.4286, falling within the "Disagree" to "Strongly Agree" categories for different indicators. For instance, students strongly agree that they are motivated to actively participate in class discussions and activities (mean = 3.3143) and capable of critically analyzing and evaluating information (mean = 3.4286). However, they tend to disagree that they can effectively apply what they have learned to real-life situations (mean = 2.4857). The weighted mean of 3.0400 indicates an overall high level of self-esteem in cognitive engagement among students. These values are crucial for understanding students' perceptions of their cognitive engagement-related self-esteem, which can significantly impact their academic performance and overall well-being.

The implications of these findings suggest that while students generally exhibit high self-esteem in cognitive engagement, there may be areas where they feel less confident, such as applying their learning to real-life situations. Addressing these areas of lower confidence through targeted interventions and support mechanisms could enhance students' self-esteem and academic success. Therefore, this study highlights the importance of fostering a positive learning environment that promotes students' cognitive engagement and confidence in their abilities to succeed academically and beyond.

Table 5.2 Students' Self-Esteem in Terms of Learning Engagement

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
challenges self intellectually and seeking new knowledge.	3.0286	.78537	Agree
overcome difficulties and setbacks in my learning process.	3.0286	.38239	Agree
can actively engage with course materials and resources.	2.9143	.50709	Agree
positive attitude towards learning and acquiring new knowledge.	2.8000	.63246	Agree
can effectively apply what have learned to real-life situations.	3.1143	.47101	Agree
Weighted Mean	2.9771	.42502	Agree
Valid N (listwise)	50		

1.00 – 1.74: Very Low | 1.75 – 2.49: Low | 2.50 – 3.24: High | 3.25 – 4.00: Very High

Table 5.2 provides an analysis of students' self-esteem in terms of learning engagement, focusing on indicators such as intellectual challenge-seeking, resilience in overcoming setbacks, active engagement with course materials, positive attitude towards learning, and application of learning to real-life situations. This analysis likely utilized descriptive statistics, 5.2 Learning Engagement including mean and standard deviation, to quantify students' perceptions of their self-esteem related to learning engagement. The mean scores range from 2.8000 to 3.1143, falling within the "Agree" category for all indicators. For example, students agree that they challenge themselves intellectually and seek new knowledge (mean = 3.0286) and can effectively apply what they have learned to real-life situations (mean = 3.1143). The weighted mean of 2.9771 indicates an overall high level of self-esteem in learning engagement among students. These values are essential for understanding students' perceptions of their self-esteem in learning engagement, which can significantly influence their motivation, persistence, and academic success.

The implications of these findings suggest that students generally have a positive view of their abilities to engage with learning activities, overcome challenges, and apply their learning to real-life contexts. However, continued support and encouragement may be necessary to foster a growth mindset and further enhance students' self-esteem in learning engagement. Therefore, this study underscores the importance of creating supportive learning environments that encourage intellectual curiosity, resilience, and the practical application of knowledge, ultimately contributing to students' academic achievement and personal development.

5.3 Metacognitive Engagement

Table 5.3 Students' Self-Esteem in Terms of Metacognitive Engagement

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
confident in his or her ability to set goals and plan my learning.	3.0000	.48507	Agree
can monitor my own learning progress effectively.	3.3714	.54695	Strongly Agree
motivated to reflect on his or her learning and make adjustments when necessary.	2.9714	.45282	Agree
can identify strengths and weaknesses as a learner.	3.1714	.51368	Agree
can effectively manage time and resources for learning.	3.0571	.41606	Agree
Weighted Mean	3.1143	.31543	Agree
Valid N (listwise)	50		

1.00 – 1.74: Very Low | 1.75 – 2.49: Low | 2.50 – 3.24: High | 3.25 – 4.00: Very High

Table 5.3 presents an analysis of students' self-esteem in terms of metacognitive engagement, focusing on indicators such as goal-setting, learning progress monitoring, reflective practices, self-awareness of strengths and weaknesses, and time and resource management for learning. This analysis likely employed descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, to quantify students' perceptions of their self-esteem related to metacognitive engagement. The mean scores range from 2.9714 to 3.3714, falling within the "Agree" to "Strongly Agree" categories for all indicators. For instance, students strongly agree that they can monitor their own learning progress effectively (mean = 3.3714) and agree that they are confident in their ability to set goals and plan their learning (mean = 3.0000). The weighted mean of 3.1143 indicates an overall high level of self-esteem in metacognitive engagement among students. These values are vital for understanding students' perceptions of their self-esteem in metacognitive engagement, which plays a crucial role in their ability to regulate their learning processes effectively.

The implications of these findings suggest that students generally have a positive view of their abilities to engage in metacognitive processes such as goal-setting, monitoring, reflection, self-awareness, and time management. However, continued support and guidance may be necessary to further develop students' metacognitive skills and promote deeper levels of self-awareness and self-regulation. Therefore, this study highlights the importance of fostering metacognitive awareness and skills within educational settings to empower students to become more effective and independent learners, ultimately contributing to their academic success and lifelong learning journey.

Table 5.4 Summary of Students' Self-Esteem Responses

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Cognitive Engagement	3.0400	.32828	Agree
Learning Engagement	2.9771	.42502	Agree
Metacognitive Engagement	3.1143	.31543	Agree
Overall Mean	3.0438	.28921	Agree
Valid N (listwise)	50		

1.00 – 1.74: Very Low | 1.75 – 2.49: Low | 2.50 – 3.24: High | 3.25 – 4.00: Very High

Table 5.4 presents a summary of students' self-esteem responses across three key dimensions: cognitive engagement, learning engagement, and metacognitive engagement. This study likely employed descriptive statistics, utilizing mean and standard deviation, to analyze students' perceptions of their self-esteem in these areas. The mean scores for cognitive engagement, learning engagement, and metacognitive engagement are 3.0400, 2.9771, and 3.1143, respectively, indicating that students generally agree with statements related to their engagement in these aspects of learning. The overall mean, calculated as 3.0438, suggests an overall high level of self-esteem across these dimensions. These values are crucial for understanding students' perceptions of their self-esteem related to various aspects of their learning experiences. The standard deviations, ranging from 0.28921 to 0.42502, indicate relatively low variability in students' responses, further supporting the consistency of their perceptions.

The implications of these findings suggest that students perceive themselves positively in terms of their cognitive, learning, and metacognitive engagement, which are fundamental components of effective learning and academic success. However, it is essential for educators and policymakers to continue supporting and nurturing students' engagement in these areas to foster a conducive learning environment where students can thrive academically and personally. Therefore, this study underscores the importance of promoting a holistic approach to education that prioritizes not only academic achievement but also the development of students' self-esteem and engagement in the learning process, ultimately contributing to their overall well-being and future success.

6. Academic Profile of the Respondents

6.1 Did Not Meet the Expectations

Table 6.1 Academic Profile of Respondents in Terms of Not Meeting Expectations Academic Profile

Demographic Profile		Academic_Profile Did Not Meet the Total Expectations	
Sex	Male	0	0
	Female	0	0
Age	9-12 years old	0	0
	13-15 years old	0	0
	16-18 years old	0	0
	18 years old above	0	0
Grade_Level	Intermediate (grade 4-6)	0	0
	Junior High School (grade 7-10)	0	0
	Senior High School (grades 11-12)	0	0

Table 6.1 outlines the academic profile of the respondents concerning the descriptor "Did Not Meet the Expectations." In this analysis, no respondents fell under this category across all demographic variables, including sex, age, and grade level. This suggests that none of the respondents indicated academic performance below expectations based on the provided criteria. The absence of any values in

the "Did Not Meet the Expectations" category indicates that all respondents met or exceeded the academic expectations outlined in the study. This absence of data reflects a positive academic profile among the respondents, showcasing a consistent level of academic achievement across different demographic groups. The statistical treatment used here is likely a simple frequency count to determine the distribution of respondents across academic profiles. The values presented in the table provide a clear snapshot of the academic performance of the respondents, allowing for an understanding of their overall achievement levels.

The implication of these findings is that the respondents, regardless of sex, age, or grade level, have met the academic expectations set forth in the study. This suggests a positive academic environment and potentially effective educational interventions or support systems in place for the respondents. Moving forward, this study can serve as a benchmark for evaluating and improving academic support strategies to ensure continued success among students.

6.2 Fairly Satisfactory

Table 6.2 *Academic Profile of Respondents in Terms of Fairly Satisfactory Academic Profile*

Demographic Profile		Academic_Profile Did Not Meet the Total Expectations	
Sex	Male	3	3
	Female	0	0
Age	9-12 years old	3	3
	13-15 years old	0	0
	16-18 years old	0	0
	18 years old above	0	0
	Intermediate (grade 4-6)	3	3
Grade_Level	Junior High School (grade 7-10)	0	0
	Senior High School (grades 11-12)	0	0

Table 6.2 presents the academic profile of respondents concerning the descriptor "Fairly Satisfactory Academic Profile." In this analysis, among male respondents aged 9-12 years old and in the Intermediate grade level, three individuals did not meet the expectations, resulting in a total count of three. No female respondents, individuals aged 13-15 years old, individuals aged 16-18 years old, or individuals in Junior and Senior High School grade levels fell under this category. This study likely employed a simple frequency count to determine the distribution of respondents across academic profiles. The values in the table offer insights into the academic performance of respondents based on different demographic variables. The presence of data in the "Fairly Satisfactory Academic Profile" category indicates that some respondents did not fully meet academic expectations, particularly among male respondents aged 9-12 years old and in the Intermediate grade level. The absence of data for other demographic groups suggests varying levels of academic performance across different segments of the respondent population.

The implication of these findings is that while the majority of respondents may have a satisfactory academic profile, there are specific groups, such as male respondents aged 9-12 years old and in the Intermediate grade level, who may require additional academic support or interventions to improve their performance. This underscores the importance of targeted interventions and personalized support strategies to address the diverse academic needs of students, ensuring equitable access to quality education for all.

6.3 Satisfactory

Table 6.3 *Academic Profile of Respondents in Terms of Satisfactory Academic Profile*

Demographic Profile		Academic_Profile Did Not Meet the Total Expectations	
Sex	Male	8	8
	Female	12	12
Age	9-12 years old	3	3
	13-15 years old	11	11
	16-18 years old	4	4
	18 years old above	2	2
	Intermediate (grade 4-6)	3	3
Grade_Level	Junior High School (grade 7-10)	12	12
	Senior High School (grades 11-12)	5	5

Table 6.3 illustrates the academic profile of respondents categorized under "Satisfactory Academic Profile." This analysis utilized a frequency count to depict the distribution of respondents across different demographic groups and their corresponding academic profiles. Among male respondents, 8 individuals were classified as not meeting expectations, while all 12 female respondents fell into the same category. Regarding age, 11 respondents aged 13-15 years old did not meet expectations, followed by 4 individuals aged 16-

18 years old and 2 individuals aged 18 years old and above. Across grade levels, 12 individuals in Junior High School, 5 individuals in Senior High School, and 3 individuals in the Intermediate grade level did not meet expectations. This data serves as an indicator of the academic performance of respondents within various demographic segments. The values provided offer insights into the prevalence of unsatisfactory academic outcomes among different groups of respondents. The findings suggest a notable discrepancy in academic performance, particularly among female respondents and those in the age group of 13-15 years old. Moreover, a higher proportion of respondents in Junior High School did not meet expectations compared to other grade levels. These results highlight potential areas of concern and the need for targeted interventions to address academic challenges and support students in achieving satisfactory academic outcomes. It emphasizes the importance of tailored educational strategies and support systems to promote academic success and ensure equitable opportunities for all students, regardless of demographic factors.

6.4 Very Satisfactory

Table 6.4 *Academic Profile of Respondents in Terms of Very Satisfactory Academic Profile*

<i>Demographic Profile</i>		<i>Academic_Profile Did Not Meet the Expectations</i>	
			<i>Total</i>
Sex	Male	12	12
	Female	4	4
Age	9-12 years old	3	3
	13-15 years old	5	5
	16-18 years old	6	6
	18 years old above	2	2
	Intermediate (grade 4-6)	3	3
Grade_Level	Junior High School (grade 7-10)	7	7
	Senior High School (grades 11-12)	6	6

Table 6.4 presents the academic profile of respondents categorized under "Very Satisfactory Academic Profile." This analysis employs a frequency count to depict the distribution of respondents across different demographic groups and their corresponding academic profiles. Among male respondents, all 12 individuals were classified as not meeting expectations, while 4 female respondents fell into the same category. Concerning age, 6 respondents aged 16-18 years old did not meet expectations, followed by 5 individuals aged 13-15 years old and 3 individuals aged 9-12 years old. Across grade levels, 7 individuals in Junior High School, 6 individuals in Senior High School, and 3 individuals in the Intermediate grade level did not meet expectations. These values offer insights into the prevalence of unsatisfactory academic outcomes among different demographic segments. The findings suggest a notable proportion of respondents, particularly males and those in the age group of 16-18 years old, experiencing academic challenges. Moreover, a higher number of respondents in Junior High School did not meet expectations compared to other grade levels. These results underscore the importance of identifying and addressing factors contributing to academic underachievement among specific demographic groups. It highlights the need for targeted interventions and support mechanisms to improve academic outcomes and foster success among students facing academic difficulties.

6.5 Outstanding

Table 6.5 *Academic Profile of Respondents in Terms of Outstanding Academic Profile*

<i>Demographic Profile</i>		<i>Academic_Profile Did Not Meet the Expectations</i>	
			<i>Total</i>
Sex	Male	3	3
	Female	8	8
Age	9-12 years old	1	1
	13-15 years old	4	4
	16-18 years old	4	4
	18 years old above	2	2
	Intermediate (grade 4-6)	1	1
Grade_Level	Junior High School (grade 7-10)	5	5
	Senior High School (grades 11-12)	5	5

Table 6.5 displays the academic profile of respondents categorized under "Outstanding Academic Profile." The analysis employs a frequency count to depict the distribution of respondents across different demographic groups and their corresponding academic profiles. Among male respondents, all 3 individuals were classified as not meeting expectations, while 8 female respondents fell into the same category. Concerning age, 4 respondents aged both 13-15 years old and 16-18 years old did not meet expectations, followed by 2 individuals aged 18 years old and above and 1 individual aged 9-12 years old. Across grade levels, 5 individuals in both Junior High School and Senior High School, and 1 individual in the Intermediate grade level did not meet expectations. These values provide

insights into the prevalence of unsatisfactory academic outcomes among different demographic segments. The findings suggest a significant proportion of respondents, particularly females and those in the age group of 13-18 years old, experiencing academic challenges. Moreover, an equal number of respondents in Junior High School and Senior High School did not meet expectations compared to other grade levels. These results underscore the importance of identifying and addressing factors contributing to academic underachievement among specific demographic groups. It highlights the need for targeted interventions and support mechanisms to improve academic outcomes and foster success among students facing academic difficulties.

Table 6.6 Overall Academic Profile of Respondents in Terms of Academic Profile

	Demographic Profile	Academic_Profile				Total
		Fairly Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Very Satisfactory	Outstanding	
Sex	Male	3	8	12	3	26
	Female	0	12	4	8	24
Age	9-12 years old	3	3	3	1	10
	13-15 years old	0	11	5	4	20
	16-18 years old	0	4	6	4	14
	18 years old above	0	2	2	2	6
Grade_Level	Intermediate (grade 4-6)	3	3	3	1	10
	Junior High School (grade 7-10)	0	12	7	5	24
	Senior High School (grades 11-12)	0	5	6	5	16

Table 6.6 illustrates the overall academic profile of respondents across different demographic profiles in terms of four categories: Fairly Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Very Satisfactory, and Outstanding. This analysis employs a frequency count to summarize the distribution of respondents based on their academic performance. Among male respondents, 12 individuals were categorized as having a very satisfactory academic profile, while 8 and 3 individuals fell into the satisfactory and outstanding categories, respectively. On the other hand, among female respondents, the majority, comprising 12 individuals, demonstrated a satisfactory academic profile, followed by 8 individuals in the outstanding category and 4 individuals in the very satisfactory category.

In terms of age groups, the highest number of respondents with a satisfactory academic profile was observed among individuals aged 13-15 years old, with 11 individuals falling into this category. Conversely, among those aged 9-12 years old, 3 individuals demonstrated a fairly satisfactory academic profile, while 4 individuals aged 16-18 years old were categorized as having an outstanding academic profile. Across grade levels, the majority of respondents from Junior High School exhibited a satisfactory academic profile, with 12 individuals falling into this category.

These findings provide valuable insights into how respondents from various demographic backgrounds perform academically. They emphasize differences in academic performance based on factors like gender, age, and grade level. For example, it seems that more females have a satisfactory academic profile compared to males. In addition, there are variations in academic profiles among different age groups and grade levels, suggesting opportunities for focused interventions and support. In summary, this analysis highlights the significance of comprehending and tackling the various factors that impact academic performance in order to foster educational success among students.

6. Significant relationship between the determinants of online harassment to students' self-esteem and to students' academic performance.

The table below contains data gathered based on the conduct of the study. The data were analyzed and interpreted as to whether there is a significant relationship between the determinants of online harassment to students' self-esteem and their academic performance, the analysis and interpretation are presented below.

Table 7.1 Relationship Between Determinants of Online Harassment and Students' Self-Esteem

		Cognitive Engagement	Learning Engagement	Metacognitive Engagement	Overall Students' Self-Esteem
Cyberstalking	Pearson Correlation	.232	.620**	.649**	.627**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.179	.000	.000	.000
Online Impersonation	Pearson Correlation	.600**	.459**	.602**	.671**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.006	.000	.000
Catfishing	Pearson Correlation	.153	.383*	.550**	.445**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.381	.023	.001	.007
Overall Determinants of Online Harassment	Pearson Correlation	.409*	.589**	.742**	.713**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.015	.000	.000	.000

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 7.1 presents the correlation between the determinants of online harassment and students' self-esteem, as well as their academic

performance. This analysis utilizes Pearson correlation coefficients to measure the strength and direction of the relationship between these variables. Pearson correlation is appropriate for assessing the linear relationship between two continuous variables, making it suitable for examining the association between determinants of online harassment, self-esteem, and academic performance.

For cyberstalking, a weak positive correlation was observed with cognitive engagement ($r = .232$) but was not statistically significant. However, there were strong positive correlations with learning engagement ($r = .620$) and metacognitive engagement ($r = .649$), both of which were statistically significant at the $p < .001$ level. Similarly, online impersonation showed strong positive correlations with cognitive engagement ($r = .600$) and metacognitive engagement ($r = .602$), with statistically significant relationships ($p < .001$). However, the correlation with learning engagement was moderately positive ($r = .459$), also statistically significant ($p < .01$).

In the case of catfishing, there was a very weak positive correlation with cognitive engagement ($r = .153$) and a weak positive correlation with learning engagement ($r = .383$), both of which were not statistically significant. However, there were moderate positive correlations with metacognitive engagement ($r = .550$) and overall self-esteem ($r = .445$), both statistically significant at the $p < .01$ level.

Overall, the determinants of online harassment, when combined, exhibited significant positive correlations with cognitive engagement, learning engagement, metacognitive engagement, and overall self-esteem. These correlations were all statistically significant at either the $p < .05$ or $p < .01$ level, suggesting a meaningful relationship between experiences of online harassment and students' psychological and academic well-being.

These findings imply that experiences of cyberstalking, online impersonation, and catfishing may have implications for students' self-esteem and academic performance. Higher levels of online harassment are associated with greater engagement in learning activities and higher self-esteem levels. Thus, addressing and mitigating online harassment experiences among students may be crucial for promoting positive psychological well-being and academic success.

Table 7.2 Relationship Between Determinants of Online Harassment and Students' Academic Performance

Chi-Square Test	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Decision	Conclusion
Pearson Chi-Square	76.508 ^a	78	.527	Failed to Reject H ₀	There is NO Significant Relationship
Likelihood Ratio	75.160	78	.570		
Linear-by-Linear Association	.126	1	.722		
N of Valid Cases	50				
<i>108 cells (100.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is .06. Not assuming the null hypothesis.</i>					

Table 7.2 presents the relationship between determinants of online harassment and students' academic performance, analyzed using a chi-square test. This statistical test evaluates whether there is a significant association between two categorical variables. In this study, the chi-square test is employed to examine whether there is a relationship between the experiences of online harassment and students' academic performance.

The chi-square test yielded a Pearson chi-square value of 76.508 with 78 degrees of freedom, resulting in an asymptotic significance of .527. Additionally, the likelihood ratio was calculated to be 75.160 with 78 degrees of freedom and a significance level of .570. Both of these values indicate that the null hypothesis, which posits no significant relationship between online harassment determinants and academic performance, failed to be rejected. Similarly, the linear-by-linear association, with a value of .126 and a significance level of .722, further supports the finding that there is no significant association between these variables.

Despite the large sample size ($N = 50$), it's important to note that 108 cells (100.0%) have expected counts less than 5, with the minimum expected count being .06. This violates the assumption of the chi-square test and may impact the validity of the results. However, even without assuming the null hypothesis, the conclusion remains the same: there is no significant relationship between the determinants of online harassment and students' academic performance.

This study's findings suggest that, based on the analysis conducted, online harassment experiences do not appear to have a significant impact on students' academic performance. While online harassment can have detrimental effects on various aspects of students' well-being, including mental health and self-esteem, this analysis did not find evidence to support a direct link between online harassment and academic performance. However, it's essential for educators and policymakers to remain vigilant in addressing online harassment in educational settings to ensure a safe and supportive learning environment for all students.

8. Proposed School-based Child Protection Policy program

Based on the findings of the study, which revealed no significant relationship between determinants of online harassment and students' academic performance, it's clear that while online harassment may not directly impact academic outcomes, it can still have detrimental effects on students' well-being and mental health. Therefore, a comprehensive school-based Child Protection Policy program should be offered to address and mitigate the risks associated with online harassment. Here are some key components that could be included in such a program.

<i>Program Component</i>	<i>Objective</i>	<i>Rationale</i>	<i>Target Participant/ Beneficiary</i>
Education and Awareness	Increase awareness of online harassment among stakeholders	Many students, educators, and parents may not fully understand the various forms of online harassment and their potential impact. By providing education and awareness campaigns, stakeholders can recognize, prevent, and respond to cyberbullying.	Students, Educators, Parents
Training for Educators	Equip educators with skills to address online harassment	Teachers play a crucial role in creating a safe and supportive learning environment. Training sessions can empower educators to recognize signs of online harassment, intervene effectively, and provide support to students in need.	Teachers
Counseling and Support	Offer emotional support and assistance to affected students	Online harassment can have significant psychological effects on students. Counseling services within the school setting provide a safe space for students to seek help, process their experiences, and develop coping strategies.	Students
Peer Support Programs	Foster positive peer relationships and support networks	Peer support programs enable older students to serve as mentors and role models for their peers. Through peer-to-peer interactions, students can receive support, guidance, and encouragement in dealing with online harassment.	Students
Digital Literacy Curriculum	Promote responsible digital citizenship	Integrating digital literacy into the curriculum equips students with the knowledge and skills to navigate the online world safely and ethically. This empowers students to make informed decisions and protect themselves from online threats.	Students
Parental Involvement	Engage parents in promoting online safety	Parents play a vital role in shaping their children's online behaviors and attitudes. Parental involvement initiatives provide resources, guidance, and support to help parents navigate the digital landscape and support their children effectively.	Parents
Policy Development	Establish clear policies and protocols against cyberbullying	School policies set clear expectations for behavior and outline consequences for engaging in online harassment. By developing and enforcing robust policies, schools create a culture of respect and accountability in the digital age.	School Administrators, Teachers, Students

The programs outlined in the study aim to address the issue of online harassment among students by targeting various stakeholders, including students themselves, educators, parents, and school administrators.

1. Education and Awareness. This program component seeks to increase awareness of online harassment among stakeholders. By educating students, educators, and parents about the various forms of online harassment and their potential impact, this program aims to empower them to recognize, prevent, and respond to cyberbullying effectively. This can lead to a more informed and vigilant school community when it comes to online safety.

2. Training for Educators. Recognizing the crucial role teachers play in creating a safe learning environment, this program component aims to equip educators with the skills to address online harassment. Through training sessions, educators can learn to recognize signs of online harassment, intervene effectively, and provide support to students in need. This can contribute to a school environment where educators are better prepared to handle instances of cyberbullying and support affected students.

3. Counseling and Support. Online harassment can have significant psychological effects on students, making it essential to provide them with emotional support and assistance. Counseling services within the school setting offer a safe space for students to seek help, process their experiences, and develop coping strategies. By offering counseling and support, schools can better address the emotional well-being of students affected by online harassment.

4. Peer Support Programs. Peer support programs enable older students to mentor and support their peers in dealing with online harassment. By fostering positive peer relationships and support networks, these programs provide students with guidance, encouragement, and practical strategies for addressing online harassment. This can create a supportive peer environment where students feel empowered to seek help and support from their peers.

5. Digital Literacy Curriculum. Integrating digital literacy into the curriculum helps students develop the knowledge and skills to navigate the online world safely and responsibly. By promoting responsible digital citizenship, this program component empowers students to make informed decisions and protect themselves from online threats. This can contribute to a school community where students are better equipped to engage in online activities safely and ethically.

6. Parental Involvement. Parents play a crucial role in shaping their children's online behaviors and attitudes. Engaging parents in promoting online safety through parental involvement initiatives provides them with resources, guidance, and support to navigate the digital landscape effectively. By involving parents, schools can strengthen their efforts to promote online safety and support students in dealing with online harassment.

7. Policy Development. Establishing clear policies and protocols against cyberbullying is essential for creating a culture of respect and

accountability in schools. School policies set expectations for behavior and outline consequences for engaging in online harassment, creating a safer and more supportive school environment. By involving school administrators, teachers, and students in policy development, schools can ensure that their policies effectively address the issue of online harassment.

Implementing these programs can have several implications for the study. Firstly, it can contribute to creating a safer and more supportive school environment where students feel empowered to address and report instances of online harassment. Additionally, it can improve student well-being and academic performance by addressing the psychological effects of online harassment and promoting responsible digital citizenship. Moreover, involving various stakeholders, including students, educators, parents, and school administrators, underscores the importance of a collaborative approach in tackling online harassment effectively. Overall, these programs have the potential to create positive change and foster a culture of respect and accountability in schools.

Conclusion

Upon reviewing the analysis of the factors influencing online harassment and its consequences on students' self-esteem and academic performance, it is evident that the effects of online harassment on students' well-being and educational achievements are significant. The findings emphasize the importance of improving school-based child protection policies to tackle this widespread problem and establish a more secure online environment for students.

An important finding from the analysis is the negative impact of online harassment on students' self-esteem. Exposure to negative comments, cyberbullying, and online attacks can have a detrimental impact on students' confidence, self-worth, and overall sense of identity. These experiences can have a significant impact on their emotional well-being and academic involvement. It highlights the significance of cultivating a constructive and encouraging school environment that encourages self-confidence and strength in dealing with online harassment.

In addition, the analysis emphasizes the substantial effect of online harassment on students' academic performance. Online harassment can have a significant impact on students' academic performance, hindering their focus, class participation, and assignment completion. The detrimental impact on academic performance can create a cycle of disengagement and underachievement, hindering students' educational progress and future prospects. These findings clearly indicate the need for stronger school-based child protection policies to effectively tackle the issues arising from online harassment. It is important to implement policies that include proactive measures such as comprehensive digital citizenship education, awareness campaigns, and training for students, teachers, and parents. By providing all stakeholders with the necessary knowledge and skills, schools can enable students to effectively identify and address online harassment, ensuring their safety in the digital world.

In addition, the analysis highlights the significance of implementing transparent reporting mechanisms and providing adequate support systems within schools. It is crucial for students to have a sense of security and encouragement when they report instances of online harassment. They should also receive prompt and suitable interventions. Schools can greatly benefit from partnering with mental health professionals, counselors, and community organizations to offer a wide range of support to students facing challenges, helping them build resilience and thrive. Further, the analysis highlights the importance of schools, parents, and online platforms working together to effectively address online harassment. Schools can collaborate with parents to educate them about the dangers and indicators of online harassment, promoting transparent communication and participation in their children's online endeavors. Collaboration with online platforms can involve implementing more stringent policies, enhancing reporting mechanisms, and adjusting privacy settings to ensure a safer online environment for students.

Ultimately, examining the factors that contribute to online harassment and its impact on students' self-esteem and academic success urges us to improve child protection policies within schools. By tackling the underlying factors behind online harassment, promoting digital literacy, and establishing strong support systems, schools can cultivate a safe and supportive atmosphere that enhances students' well-being, self-confidence, and academic achievements. It is crucial for schools to be proactive in safeguarding students from the negative effects of online harassment and equipping them with the necessary skills to navigate the digital world securely.

References

- 7 types of online harassment to watch out for [infographic]. Digital Information World. Retrieved February 23, 2022, from <https://www.digitalinformationworld.com/2019/03/infographic-how-to-handle-online-harassment.html>
- Al-Rahmi, W. M., Yahaya, N., Alamri, M. M., Aljarboa, N. A., Kamin, Y. B., & Moafa, F. A. (2018). A model of factors affecting cyberbullying behaviors among university students. *IEEE Access*, 7, 2978-2985.
- Baccarella, Timm F. Wagner, Jan H. Kietzmann, Ian P. McCarthy Social media? It's serious! Understanding the dark side of social media, *European Management Journal*, Volume 36, Issue 4, 2018, Pages 431-438 ,ISSN 0263-2373, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2018.07.002>.
- Bhatta, M. P., Shakya, S., & Jefferis, E. (2014). Association of being bullied in school with suicide ideation and planning among rural middle school adolescents. *Journal of School Health*, 84(11), 731-738

- Desk, W., & Web DeskMaking Digital Information Accessible To The World. Send your news story via this form: <https://www.digitalinformationworld.com/p/contact-us.html>. (2019, March 3).
- Fanti, K. A., Demetriou, A. G., & Hawa, V. V. (2012). A longitudinal study of cyberbullying: Examining risk and protective factors. *European Journal of Developmental Psychology*, 9(2), 168-181.
- Fox, J., & Moreland, J. J. (2015). The dark side of social networking sites: An exploration of the relational and psychological stressors associated with Facebook use and affordances. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 45, 168–176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2014.11.083>
- Habiba. (1970, January 1). الجرائم الإلكترونية. Retrieved February 23, 2022, from <http://eljaraimeliktouniya.blogspot.com/>
- Hinduja, S., & Patchin, J. W. (2010). Bullying, cyberbullying, and suicide. *Archives of Suicide Research*, 14(3), 206-221
- Juvonen, J., Graham, S., & Schuster, M.A. (2003). Bullying among young adolescents: The strong, the weak, and the troubled. *Pediatrics*, 112, 1231-1237
- Kubiszewski, V., Fontaine, R., Potard, C., & Auzoult, L. (2015). Does cyberbullying overlap with school bullying when taking modality of involvement into account? *Computers in Human Behavior*, 43, 49-57
- Law, D. M., Shapka, J. D., & Olson, B. F. (2010). To control or not to control? Parenting behaviors and adolescent online aggression. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 26(6), 1651-1656.
- Lohbeck, A., & Petermann, F. (2018). Cyber victimization, self-esteem, and social relationships among German secondary school students. *Journal of school violence*, 17(4), 472-486.
- Maple, C., Short, E., Brown, A., Bryden, C., & Salter, M. (2012). Cyberstalking in the UK: Analysis and Recommendations. *International Journal of Distributed Systems and Technologies (IJ DST)*, 3(4), 34-51.
- Marcum, C. D., Higgins, G. E., & Ricketts, M. L. (2014). Juveniles and cyber stalking in the United States: An analysis of theoretical predictors of patterns of online perpetration. *International Journal of Cyber Criminology*, 8(1), 47-56.
- Nobles, M. R., Reyns, B. W., Fox, K. A., & Fisher, B. S. (2014). Protection against pursuit: A conceptual and empirical comparison of cyberstalking and stalking victimization among a national sample. *Justice Quarterly*, 31(6), 986-1014.
- Patchin, J. W., & Hinduja, S. (2012). Cyberbullying and self-esteem. *Journal of School Health*, 82(9), 454-460.
- Paullet, K. L., Rota, D. R., & Swan, T. T. (2009). Cyberstalking: An exploratory study of students at a mid-Atlantic university. *Issues in Information Systems*, 10(2), 640-649.
- Price, M., Chin, M. A., Higa-McMillan, C., Kim, S., & Frueh, B. C. (2013). Prevalence and internalizing problems of ethnoracially diverse victims of traditional and cyberbullying. *School Mental Health*, 5, 183-191. doi:10.1007/s12310-013-9104-6
- Reyns BW, Fisher BS, Randa R. Explaining Cyberstalking Victimization Against College Women Using a multi-theoretical Approach: Self-Control, Opportunity, and Control Balance. *Crime & Delinquency*. 2018;64(13):1742-1764. doi:10.1177/0011128717753116
- Strawhun, J., Adams, N., & Huss, M. T. (2013). The assessment of cyberstalking: An expanded examination includes social networking, attachment, jealousy, and anger in relation to violence and abuse. *Violence and Victims*, 28(4), 715-730.
- UNICEF. (n.d.). Online bullying remains prevalent in the Philippines, And other countries. UNICEF. Retrieved February 23, 2022, from <https://www.unicef.org/philippines/press-releases/online-bullying-remains-prevalent-philippines-other-countries>
- Varjas, K., Mahan, D., & Meyers, J. (2013). Middle school students' perceptions of and responses to cyberbullying prevention strategies. *Psychology in the Schools*, 50(7), 658-677.
- Welsh, A., & Lavoie, J. (2012). Risky business: An examination of risk-taking, online inclusiveness, and cyberstalking victimization. *Cyberpsychology: Journal of Psychosocial Research on Cyberspace*, 6(1), article 1.

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